

Preliminary Observations Concerning Music for the *Kwangkay* Secondary Mortuary Ritual of the Dayak Benuaq (East Kalimantan, Indonesian Borneo)

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Abstract

This study examines some musical aspects of the secondary mortuary ritual celebrated by the Dayak Benuaq, an indigenous ethnic group inhabiting the East Kalimantan province of Indonesian Borneo. After briefly describing the three stages of their funerary practices, I will focus on some aspects of the music featured in the last of such practices, the *kwangkay*, a ritual which enables the spirits of the dead, called the *liau* and the *kelelungan*, to reach their final destinations. Music has a key role within this ritual, helping to guide the spirits of the dead to their final abode. The task is accomplished through the chanting of the *tempu* myths. Instrumental music is also played within this ritual, providing entertainment for the spirits of the dead. After analysing the organological characteristics of the instruments of the musical ensemble used for the *kwangkay*, I will concentrate on the musical pieces played. The result of this analysis shows that the music played in the context of this ritual has various recurrent oppositional features, which may refer to the dichotomy between the *liau* and the *kelelungan* spirits.¹

Osservazioni preliminari sulla musica del kwangkay, il rituale funebre secondario celebrato dai Dayak Benuaq (Kalimantan orientale, Borneo indonesiano). Il presente articolo prende in esame alcuni aspetti musicali del rituale funebre secondario celebrato dai Dayak Benuaq, un gruppo etnico della provincia di Kalimantan orientale, nel Borneo indonesiano. Dopo aver descritto brevemente i tre stadi in cui sono articolati i rituali funebri

¹ The present article is a revised and enriched version of my paper “Some musical aspects of the Kwangkay ritual of the Dayak Benuaq (East Kalimantan, Indonesia)” published in the *Borneo Research Bulletin*, vol. XLVI.

dei Benuaq, l'articolo si concentra su alcuni aspetti della musica che accompagna l'ultimo di questi, il kwangkay, un rito che permette agli spiriti dei morti, chiamati liau e kelelungan, di raggiungere l'aldilà. La musica ha un ruolo chiave in questa celebrazione, in quanto è utilizzata per guidare gli spiriti dei morti alla volta della loro destinazione finale. Questo compito è realizzato attraverso il canto dei miti tempu. Oltre a quella vocale, la musica strumentale è presente in questo rituale, in quanto è considerata come intrattenimento per gli spiriti dei morti. Dopo un esame delle caratteristiche organologiche degli strumenti musicali facenti parte dell'ensemble utilizzato, l'articolo si concentra sui brani suonati nel kwangkay. I risultati dell'analisi mostrano come le musiche eseguite in questo rituale siano caratterizzate da ricorrenti tratti dicotomici, i quali potrebbero riflettere l'opposizione tra gli spiriti liau e kelelungan.

1. Introduction

The Dayak Benuaq people inhabit the southern districts (*kecamatan*) of the West Kutai Regency (*Kabupaten Kutai Barat*) of the East Kalimantan Province (*Provinsi Kalimantan Timur*) of Indonesian Borneo (Fig. 1). Generally considered as belonging to the Luangan Dayak group, they are closely related to the Bentian, with whom they share a number of cultural traits – such as «language, ritual practice, cosmological beliefs, and cultural history» (Payne 2012: 313). The ritual practices of the Benuaq are particularly complex and elaborate. Those that are the most relevant for this article are their funerary practices, which include their secondary mortuary ritual, called the *kwangkay*.

Music plays an important role within this ritual, although its significance has never been fully emphasized. Exhaustive accounts of the *kwangkay* have been written by several authors – such as Massing (1981) and Zahorka (2013) – but they mostly deal with ethnographic aspects of this ritual. As far as I know, a detailed analysis of the musical aspects of this ritual has never been carried out.

The following article is based on my personal experiences in the West Kutai Regency villages, within the area that extends from the Jempang to the Melak districts, during two field-trips that I made in 2011. On this occasion I had the opportunity to observe all the ceremonies that mark the various phases of funerary rituals, involving a number of different families and villages. However, a detailed analysis of the many complex musical aspects of the *kwangkay* ritual would have required a longer investigation in the field, which I was not able to conduct at that time. For this reason, I will mainly refer to ethnographic data provided by other scholars, while occasionally including data that I collected from my interlocutors. The information in this article regarding music is mainly based on my own field research. The analysis of this material leads me to conclude that many musical aspects of the *kwangkay* ritual are permeated by significant dichotomies.

In the first section of this study I briefly delineate the funerary practices of the Benuaq and provide an introduction to the main characteristics of the *kwangkay* ritual. In the

FIGURE 1. Benuaq territories (Massing 1981).

second section I analyse some of its musical aspects and various issues relating to them. I have divided this latter section into two parts, one dealing with the organological features of the musical instruments involved, and the other containing a detailed analysis of the music sung and played during this ritual.

2. A general overview of the funerary practices of the Benuaq

According to the beliefs of the Benuaq people, upon death the soul of the human being (called *juus*) is transformed into the *liau*, associated with physical aspects of the body, and the *kelelungan* (or *kelelungan kelangun*), associated with the intellect or the head (Massing 1982: 61; Gönner 2000: 72). Both the *liau* and the *kelelungan* move away to temporarily reside in a sort of cosmic location, connected respectively with the bones and the skull of the deceased, who has entered a state of deep unconsciousness, as yet neither pertaining completely to the realm of the living, nor belonging to that of the dead. This liminal period ends when the final funerary ritual – the *kwangkay* – is celebrated. This ritual allows the spirits of the dead to reach their final destinations, the *Saikng Lumut*, for the *liau*, and the *Tenang kai Solai*, for the *kelelungan*.

Death is the starting point for a series of funerary practices, typically lasting for several years. They are divided into three stages, corresponding to the inhumation of the corpse immediately after death, the separation of the flesh from the bones, and the final deposition of the bones, which marks the time when the spirits reach the land of the ancestors (Massing 1981: 89). Each of these three stages is clearly marked by a ceremony, which my interlocutors called *parepm api*, *kenyau* and *kwangkay*.

The third and final ritual of the funerary practices of the Benuaq is the *kwangkay*. This very complex and elaborate ceremony consists of several phases, at the end of which the spirits of the dead are able to reach their final abode. Even though I did not have the possibility to observe all the stages of this lengthy ritual, I was able to witness a number of its phases in various different circumstances, involving different villages and families, and thus to analyse their features.

3. Some musical aspects of the *kwangkay* ritual

Music plays a key role within the *kwangkay*, with functions that are central to the development of the whole ritual. In fact it accomplishes the main purpose of the ceremony, which is to guide the *liau* and the *kelelungan* spirits of the dead to their final destinations, and it is also used to please them, by providing them with entertainment. In any case, whether it is a vehicle for guiding them to their final destinations or a way to please them, music within the *kwangkay* can be considered as a medium of communication between this world and the after-world.

I believe, moreover, that music has a particularly important role within this ceremony, as it seems to reflect the dichotomy between the *liau* and the *kelelungan* spirits, a dualistic opposition that is central to this ritual. As pointed out by Sillander (2012: 66) in reference to the Bentian, this oppositional character may

express basic human concerns [...], their ambiguous association with a typically remote afterworld (often located in heaven), on the one hand, and the grave and the land where they used to live, on the other, an ambiguity reflecting the ambivalent relationship of the soul with the body, being both associated with and separable from it. The *liau/kelelungan* distinction may indeed partly reflect this logic; the more malevolent and essentially useless *liau* being associated with the body, its animation, and earth, and the more benevolent *kelelungan* with the head, the so-called higher human capacities, and heaven. However, more importantly it represents the two-sided significance of death – simultaneously debilitating and (potentially) revitalizing – and two widely employed and studied strategies of responding to it: separation and regeneration.

The “good” *kelelungan* is opposed to the “bad” *liau* (Sillander 2012: 65) but both of them are generated from the unique soul of a human being, and are therefore conceived as oppositional features or separate aspects of the single unity of a person’s individual identity. To a similar extent, the presence of music in the context of the *kwangkay* may reflect this dichotomy, while also bringing a series of oppositional features together into one unity. An initial dichotomy can be found in the contrasting kinds of music within this ritual: vocal music – to establish a communication with the *liau* and the *kelelungan* spirits – and instrumental music – to entertain them. The presence of such oppositional features constitutes a recurring theme in my musical analysis of the *kwangkay*.

4. Reciting the *temputn* myths

As mentioned above, the purpose of the *kwangkay* is to allow the *kelelungan* and the *liau* spirits to reach their final destinations. In order to do so, the *sentangih* – the man who conducts the ritual – guides them and helps them to overcome the many obstacles they encounter during their journey. He does this by means of offerings and, most importantly, by reciting the *temputn* myths, sitting, together with his assistant or assistants, next to the *selimat*, a wooden box in which the skulls of the deceased are preserved (Fig. 2). These myths, believed to be accounts of real events, provide a genealogy of the spirits and convey the most important concepts and beliefs of the Benuaq culture, in a poetic, highly archaic style full of metaphors (Hopes *et al.* 1997: 2).

The reciting of these myths takes the form of singing, which continues for the whole period of the ritual, during the day as well as at night. As far as I am aware, these myths can be sung in various different ways, but I will only focus on the way they are recited shortly before the *ngerangkau* musical piece is played. On this occasion, the *sentangih* divides these long myths into verses, the ending of which is marked by his assistant or assistants, who emphasise what the *sentangih* has sung by accompanying him in singing the last verse heterophonically. In one of my recordings each of the verses sung by the *sentangih* was always followed by a sort of choral refrain, sung by him together with his

FIGURE 2. The *sentangih* and his assistant next to the *selimat* (photo: V. Della Ratta).

assistants, clearly constituting an “a\b” or “verse-refrain” form. The transcription of a section from this recording is provided below (Fig. 3).²

In my transcription the melody sung by the *sentangih*, which rarely exceeds a range of one octave, has a syncopated rhythm, characterized by a succession of ascending and descending musical phrases consisting of dotted eighth notes (quavers) and sixteenth notes (semiquavers). This pattern slightly relaxes at the end of the verse, as well as in the refrain when the *sentangih*'s assistants sing together with him, with some longer notes that give the melody a less constrained quality. Each of the verses as well as the refrains sung by the *sentangih* and his assistants have a fixed duration (4 bars in my transcription), the final extended notes of which merge into the new section, whether this is the refrain or the verse.

In various other recordings I made during my fieldwork this type of alternation between two distinct sections was lacking, and the *sentangih* sang a series of repetitions of

² This transcription was made using conventional western notation, with additional signs for rendering the many vocal effects and embellishments added by the singer(s). In order to facilitate the reading, I have simplified the writing of some parts, providing them with a more regular rhythm, which is sometimes slightly unclear and unstable in the actual recording. The complete audio recording from which the section analysed here is taken is available on Della Ratta (2016), track 1, side B. [Audio example 1](#) is an excerpt of this.

♩ = 84 approx.

5

~ = embellishment

FIGURE 3. An excerpt from the singing of the *tempuŋ* myths.

the same verse, or section, with the end of each one being emphasised by his assistants.³ However, in all the cases I have witnessed, after some minutes the *sentangih* always started to sing a much more complex and embellished melody with frequent melismas, the ending of which was emphasised by his assistants. This development constitutes a new section in which the intensity of the singing increases, eventually leading to the start of the *ngerangkau* musical piece.

The dichotomous oppositions I have referred to above are therefore present in the singing of the *tempuŋ* myths in various ways. First of all there is the opposition between the solo singing of the *sentangih* and the choral singing together with his assistant(s). Then there is a contrast between the syncopated rhythm sung by the *sentangih* and the more regular rhythm with which the choir sings the end of the verses (or the refrain when this is included) together with him. Finally, the more plain and simple melody of the verses (and refrains) at the start of the piece contrasts with the final section, full of embellishments and melismas, which is a prelude to the beginning of the *ngerangkau*.

5. Musical instruments

The centrality of the role of music within the *kwangkay* is also revealed by the fact that musicians are selected by the *pelalus* – the organizer of the ritual – who provides them with the musical instruments that will be used for the ceremony (Zahorka 2013: 196). The musical ensemble of the *kwangkay* ritual consists of three instruments: gongs or kettles placed horizontally in a row on a rack, vertically suspended gongs hanging from the wall of the house, and very long drums tied to the wall of the house. It belongs to the wider category of the *kulintang*-type ensembles, which are widespread in several areas of Southeast Asia (Maceda 2001).

The long drums, called *gimbar*,⁴ are carved from a tree trunk and can be up to two meters long. They have a tubular or conical shape, with one end covered with an animal

³ This recording is available on Della Ratta (2016), track 1, side A. Video footage is in the [video example 1](#).

⁴ According to Zahorka (2013), Yampolsky (1998), and Maceda (2001) it is called *gimar*, while Massing (1981) refers to it as *gimer*.

FIGURE 4. A player of the *kentangan* kettles. In the background *gimbar* drums and *gningt* gongs can be seen (photo: V. Della Ratta).

FIGURE 5. The lay-out of the *kentangan* kettles as seen by the player.

skin, and the other left open. Because of their length these drums are attached diagonally to the wall of the house, and the drummers, standing next to them, beat them with a wooden stick. Two or three drums can be included in the ensemble.

The *gningt*⁵ (a generic word for “gong” or “gongs”) are vertically suspended gongs, the number of which rarely exceeds seven. These gongs hang at the bottom of the wall and the player or players sit down cross-legged to play them with a mallet. The *gimbar* drums and the *gningt* gongs provide the drone or *ostinato* over which the melody is played by the *kentangan*.

The *kentangan*⁶ is a gong chime instrument consisting of six kettles suspended horizontally in a row on a wooden frame, vaguely resembling a Javanese *bonang* but smaller in size (even though the *kentangan* is sometimes referred to as *saron*; Fig. 4). The high-tone kettles are positioned on the left-hand side of the instrument, while the low-tone kettles are positioned on the right (Fig. 5). The player uses a wooden stick in his left hand to play the accompaniment and another in his right hand to play the melody, and the resulting music has a sort of intermittent high pitch bourdon, which sustains the lower-pitched melody. The technique for playing this instrument is rather particular, as the *kentangan* kettles are played in such a way that the wooden stick rebounds rapidly upon the surface of the kettle to create a tremolo effect.

There is no standard tuning for this ensemble (like other *kulintang*-type ensembles, as reported by Maceda 2001) and, as far as I could determine, the musical scales to which these instruments are tuned differ widely from one village to another, as well as from one instrumental set to another. This also seems to apply to Yampolsky’s reference to the way in which two different *kentangan* kettle sets that he recorded were tuned. He states that «the tuning of the *kentangan* (ascending) is approximately G[#] B C[#] D E G natural» in one case,

⁵ According to Zahorka (2013) and Maceda (2001) it is called *genikng*, according to Massing (1981) *gendong*, and according to Yampolsky (1998) *geniqng*.

⁶ Zahorka (2013) also refers to it as *saron*. Massing (1981) calls it *kelentangan*, whereas Maceda (2001) calls it *klentangan*.

FIGURE 6A-B. Pitch measurements of two *gningt* gongs (A) and two *kentangan* kettle sets (B).

and «G A C D Eb F#» in the other (Yampolsky 1998: 19-20). In my fieldwork I measured two different sets of *gningt* gongs and *kentangan* kettles, the results of which are shown in Figure 6A-B. I found no apparent correspondences between the tuning of these instruments and was thus unable to establish whether a single basic scale exists in Benuak music.

6. The *ngerangkau*

The term *ngerangkau* refers both to the musical piece and to the dance performed during the *kwangkay* ritual. This piece is played two times every night for the duration of the whole ceremony, after the *mungkaaq selimat* ritual has been performed (see Venz 2014), and it accompanies the separate dances of the men and the women (Fig. 7). It can also be played on other occasions, such as when people are returning home from a sacrifice, but its basic function is always that of providing entertainment for the spirits (Massing 1981: 93). During my fieldwork period I recorded this piece on five different occasions in various different villages, featuring a variety of different instrumental sets and musicians. The following account is based on the analysis of these recordings.

One of the most interesting aspects of the *ngerangkau* is its syncopated rhythm, which in my opinion constitutes its most distinctive feature. It has a pattern consisting of thirteen beats that produces an irregular limping rhythm. Even though the thirteenth beat is occasionally played with hesitation, in a way that slightly delays the recommencement of the thirteen-beat metrical unit and gives the impression of a fourteen-beat pattern, in all the recordings that I examined there is a clear prevalence of the thirteen-beat pattern. Yampolsky, who recorded (out of context) and analyzed the excerpt of the *ngerangkau* released by Smithsonian Folkways, stated that «metrically, *ngerangkau* is built up of fours, but its rhythm has a curious limping quality» (Yampolsky 1998: 20). It thus appears that he did not identify it as a thirteen-beat metrical pattern. However, elsewhere Yampolsky (2015: 170-1) – discussing Indonesian music characterized by a «complex meter» (which can be found in Nusa Tenggara, as well as in Kalimantan) – described a piece belonging to the Tunjung, an ethnic

FIGURE 7. An ensemble playing the *ngerangkau* (photo: V. Della Ratta).

group close to the Benuaq, as being based on a thirteen-beat pattern. This piece has many striking similarities to the *ngerangkau*. Moreover, its name on the track listing of the album that Yampolsky referred to in his article (*muwankai*) closely resembles the name of the ritual (*kwangkay*) in the context of which the Benuaq play the *ngerangkau*.⁷

The *gimbar* drum players emphasize the rhythmic unit by playing in unison, with basically no variations throughout the duration of the piece. The following figure shows that the rhythmic patterns of the five different versions of the piece I analyzed had only a few minor variations from a fairly well defined rhythmical pattern (Fig. 8).

In the five versions of the piece I analyzed I was unable to identify a single basic pattern that the *gningt* suspended gongs adhered to. In fact it probably depends on the number of the gongs that are being played and the number of players, and thus the complexity of their interactions. The following transcription of an excerpt from the *ngerangkau* is a good example of a typical basic pattern (Fig. 9).⁸

⁷ See Gomes and Mignon 1998, track 17.

⁸ I have decided to use the conventional western notation in order to facilitate the reading of my transcriptions, although there is not always an exact correspondence to the actual pitch of the instruments. Moreover, both the *kentangan* kettles and the *gimbar* drums are occasionally played so that the stick re-

FIGURE 8. An analysis of five different versions of *gimbar* drum patterns.

$\text{♩} = 242 \text{ approx.}$

FIGURE 9. An excerpt from the *ngerangkau*.

This is the transcription of a short excerpt from a *ngerangkau* piece that I recorded, which I feel is particularly suitable for musical analysis, as this basic structure – consisting of six metrical units of thirteen beats – was played constantly for the whole duration of the piece. The reiteration of well-defined patterns by both the *gimbar* drums and the *gningt* suspended gongs is very evident in the transcription, and these instruments repeated the same pattern for the whole duration of the piece with hardly any variations. Also the *kentangan* kettles reiterated a melodic sequence, consisting of six melodic phrases, with minor variations. In fact, upon analyzing my field-recordings I realized that, even though the melody played is not fixed and invariable, the *kentangan* kettles reiterate a sequence of various melodic phrases with a certain regularity.

In the transcription I have provided the melodic sequence reiterated by the *kentangan* kettles player consists of six melodic phrases, while in the other versions I examined it consisted of five, six or eight. Even though the number of the phrases can vary, the

bounds on the surface of the instrument (either the kettle or the drum head) to create a particular tremolo effect, which I have not indicated in the transcriptions. The excerpt transcribed here is in the [audio example 2](#), whereas the complete recording is available on Della Ratta (2016), track 1, side B.

kentangan kettles play the sequence repeatedly for the whole duration of the piece – which can last up to about forty minutes.

In my transcription the melodic sequence of the *kentangan* kettles starts with a melodic phrase, repeated twice, characterized by an ascending profile. Then a pattern characterized by a rather centric-ascending profile is juxtaposed with another rather centric. These are both played twice and the whole sequence restarts, constituting a basic melodic sequence of a|a|b|c|b|c. The melody of the *kentangan* kettles is embellished by a sort of high-pitch bourdon, played with a tremolo effect. As can be seen in the transcription, the players followed the a|a|b|c|b|c pattern of melodic phrases quite faithfully, with very few variations.

7. The *kangkang kangkot*

Sometimes the *ngerangkau* is followed by another piece featuring a different dance, called the *kangkang kangkot*, and then repeated. This variant on the normal (*biasa*) *ngerangkau* thus has a tripartite structure consisting of three sections, each one separated from the next by a short pause. I was able to listen to the *kangkang kangkot* and record it on two separate occasions, and the following comments are based on this material. Below is the transcription of an excerpt from the *kangkang kangkot* that I recorded (Fig. 10).⁹

The *kangkang kangkot* has a binary rhythmical pattern consisting of four beats, basically devoid of syncopation. All the players embellish their part more richly than is the case for the *ngerangkau*, as shown by the transcription. The melodic pattern of the *kentangan* kettles occupies the length of one rhythmical unit (four beats) and consists of two phrases (a and b), the first with a more ascending character and the second with a rather descending or centric profile, each of which is repeated twice to create the following structure: a|a|b|b. As in the *ngerangkau*, the alternation of these melodic sections played by the *kentangan* kettles is repeated for the whole duration of the piece rather regularly.

The *kangkang kangkot* is unlike the *ngerangkau* in many ways, and it can be seen as its counterpart or opposite, thus reflecting the dichotomy that permeates the *kwangkay* ritual. Probably the main opposition is represented by the rhythm: the irregular rhythmic pattern that characterizes the *ngerangkau* is opposed to the straightforward binary rhythmic pattern of the *kangkang kangkot*.

Moreover, the longer-lasting *ngerangkau* rigidly repeats the same melodic sequence with almost no variations from the beginning till the end of the piece, while the much shorter *kangkang kangkot* is played more freely, with frequent variations and embellishments of the two basic phrases.

⁹ Excerpt in the [audio example 3](#), complete audio track available on Della Ratta (2016), track 1, side B.

♩ = 78 approx.

Kentangan

Gmingt

Gimbar

FIGURE 10. An excerpt from the *kangkang kangkot*.

Finally, a dichotomous quality can also be found in the construction of the melodic sequences that constitute the *ngerangkau* and the *kangkang kangkot*. My analysis reveals that the first piece has a more complex structure, with the single phrases intertwining in a way I have summarized as a\|b\|c\|b\|c, and a simpler structure for the latter, which can be summarized as a\|b\|b.

8. The *ngerangkau* dance

The Benuaq use the term *ngerangkau* to refer to the musical piece as well as to the dance performed during the *kwangkay*. There are two versions of the dance, the first performed by the men, the other by the women (Fig. 11). All of the dancers wear particularly elaborate headdresses. These are kept on the *selimat* before the dance begins and are only put on when the performance starts and then put back when it is over. The male and female dancers move slowly in Indian file in a counter-clockwise direction along the outer walls of the room. The dancers form a procession in the form of a ring with a more or less oval shape and they walk, taking long steps in imitation of the leader of the procession, around the *selimat* box seven times – as the number seven is conceived of as connected to the realm of death. After that they shout joyfully to mark the end of the dance.¹⁰

The oppositional character I referred to above can also be detected within the dance and is perhaps most evident in the juxtaposition between men and women. Another opposition consists in the fact that, before dancing, the male dancers take the cloths that contain the skulls of the deceased from the *selimat* (nowadays these batik cloths are wrapped around coconuts instead of skulls). They then tie these cloths over one shoulder and drape them so that the “skulls” are positioned over their backs before they start to dance. The women do not wear these cloths for their dance but they wear particular shirts used only for this occasion (usually coloured in white). Another dichotomous feature is that of the distinction between the two leaders of the dance procession and the other dancers, an opposition which is underlined by their different headdresses.

¹⁰ Video footage is in the [video examples 2](#) and [3](#).

FIGURE 11. The dance of the women (photo: V. Della Ratta).

9. Conclusions

Music is a central feature of the *kwangkay* ritual, being a medium which provides a special connection with the after-world, both in guiding the spirits of the dead to their final destinations and in entertaining them. My analysis also suggests that the musical aspects of the *kwangkay* ritual are pervaded by dichotomies, which may reflect the *liau\kelelungan* opposition. In the reciting of the *tempun* myths, the solo singing of the *sentangih* contrasts with the choir of his assistants in its melodic as well as its rhythmic aspects. As regards the instrumental music – as opposed to the vocal music provided by the *sentangih* and his assistants – the limping rhythm of the *ngerangkau* strongly contrasts with the straightforward binary rhythmic pattern of the *kangkang kangkot*. My analysis indicates that this oppositional character does not exclusively pertain to the music, as it can be found in the dance as well, as demonstrated by the dichotomies men\women, and leaders\other performers.

It seems to me that many of the musical and choreutic elements of this ritual have a fairly well-defined counterpart or opposing element, thereby emphasising a prevailing sense of dichotomous opposition, the elements of which do not generate conflict but coexist harmoniously, enclosing all the divergent aspects in a single unity.

The importance of analysing funerary rituals – and most importantly for this article the music being played within them – was well expressed by Metcalf and Huntington (1991: 25): «the issue of death throws into relief the most important cultural values by which people live their lives and evaluate their experiences. Life becomes transparent against the background of death, and fundamental social and cultural issues are revealed».

Within this conceptual framework the recurring dichotomous elements of the *kwangkay* ritual denote not only the highly refined quality of this music, while also expressing a philosophical conception that lies at the root of the Benuaq world-view: the «complementary duality» which is one of the central features of Austronesian religions of Southeast Asia (Fox 1987: 523).

Video examples

1. The *sentangih* and his assistant(s) sing the *temptn* myths.

Shot by the author in April 2011 in the district (*kecamatan*) of Melak, West Kutai Regency (*kabupaten Kutai Barat*), in the East Kalimantan Province (*Provinsi Kalimantan Timur*) of Indonesian Borneo.

2. A group of men performing the *ngerangkau* dance.

Shot by the author in April 2011 in the district (*kecamatan*) of Jempang, West Kutai Regency (*kabupaten Kutai Barat*), in the East Kalimantan Province (*Provinsi Kalimantan Timur*) of Indonesian Borneo.

3. A group of women performing the *kangkang kangkot* dance.

Same as video example 2.

Audio examples

1. The *sentangih* and his assistant(s) sing the *temptn* myths.

Recorded by the author in April 2011 in the district (*kecamatan*) of Melak, West Kutai Regency (*kabupaten Kutai Barat*), in the East Kalimantan Province (*Provinsi Kalimantan Timur*) of Indonesian Borneo.

2. An excerpt from the *ngerangkau*.

Recorded by the author in April 2011 in the district (*kecamatan*) of Jempang, West Kutai Regency (*kabupaten Kutai Barat*), in the East Kalimantan Province (*Provinsi Kalimantan Timur*) of Indonesian Borneo.

3. An excerpt from the *kangkang kangkot*.

Same as audio example 2.

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